

Traditional Practices and Folkloric Remedies Having Wound Healing Potential used by Ethnic Groups of North East Region of India

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The North East Region (NER) of India, known for its bio-resources is the Biogeographical Gateway of India as well as one of the biodiversity hotspot. Traditional knowledge has been a constructive indicator for research. This region has varied ecotypes that range from humid evergreen forest to temperate and alpine vegetations. As per census made in 2001, this region has 130 major indigenous communities and has rich heritage of herbal remedies that forms an integral part of indigenous culture. Plants are utilized for medicinal purpose since ancient times, firstly for folkloric usage and later for scientific aspects for drug development. Wound infection is a common ailment in developing countries due to poor hygienic state. Wounds are typically physical injuries which results in opening/breaking of skin thus, proper procedure for wound healing is necessary for restoration of interrupted anatomical continuity along with disorganized functional status of skin. Wounds can be classified as cuts, bruises due to external injury, burns, sores, boils, delivery wounds and abscess. The current research aims to review the traditional wound healing medicinal plants of NER of India. Hence, investigation on traditional medicine for wound healing can serve for formulation of drugs in pharmaceutical industries.

Keywords: Wound healing, North East Region of India, Traditional knowledge, folkloric remedies.